

Production of allyl chloride from chlorination of propylene

Mohammad Armanmehr*, Fatemeh Mohajer, Elham Khademloo
 Department of Chemical Technologies, Iranian Research Organization for Science and
 Technologies (IROST), P.O. Box 15815-3538, Tehran, Iran.
 Email: parastomohajer@ymail.com

Allyl chloride is the most commercially important industrial chemical. It is manufactured worldwide on a large scale. Allyl chloride is made by the non-catalytic vapor-phase chlorination of propylene at high temperature. Polymer grade propylene is used as a raw material. Chlorine gas and propylene are introduced to the chlorination reactor. The temperature of chlorination reactor is in the range of 400-600 °C, and the pressure of the chlorination reactor is in the range of 1-2 atmospheres. Chlorine gas and propylene react with each other in the chlorination reactor, and allyl chloride is produced according to the following chemical reaction

The chlorination reactor is packed with raschig tubes. Also, the reactor side inlet temperature must be at least 400 °C. Hydrochloric acid is the by-product. The reactor effluent containing unreacted propylene, hydrochloric acid, and crude allyl chloride is distilled in order to separate the propylene and hydrochloric acid from heavier components. Hydrochloric acid is absorbed in the deionized water. Unreacted propylene is recycled to the chlorination reactor. Allyl chloride is separated by distillation. The yield is 75% of theory.

References:

1. US patent 5,723,703
2. US Patent 3,120,568
3. US patent 4,319,062

